

OPTIMAL USE OF REDUNDANT MEASUREMENTS OF CONSTRAINED QUANTITIES. APPLICATION TO ELASTIC MODULI OF ANISOTROPIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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When determining material constants, it is often necessary to perform redundant tests to improve the confidence and accuracy of measurements or to obtain some constants from tests providing only algebraic combinations involving several of these constants. The quantities so obtained are generally interrelated or constrained by some conditions, which may restrain from computing the constants or using classical statistics. This paper presents a general process to resolve these difficulties, and applies it to the determination of consistent values for elastic moduli of anisotropic composite materials. The method consists of finding the minimum of some deviation function of p measured quantities. As these quantities may be dependent variables constrained by q relations, the problem is a constrained minimization problem and can be solved by the classical method of Lagrange multipliers, extremizing a modified deviation function of $p + q$ variables. The original deviation function can be a weighted quadratic function of the absolute or relative deviations between the measured quantities and their estimates, or between the inverse values. The method of Lagrange multipliers leads to a system of $p + q$ algebraic equations, which are generally non linear and may be solved numerically by an iterative method. The Newton iterative method implemented on a 4051 Tektronix microcomputer was used in the examples illustrating the method. The first example is an application to a transversely isotropic graphite-epoxy material. Seven elastic constants were measured by tension and torsion testing and the five independent elastic constants are obtained by applying the method to the measured values of these seven dependent constants. The second example uses experimental values taken from the literature for elastic compliances of an orthotropic composite material tested in several off-axis directions. The third example applies to the case of a quasi-isotropic graphite epoxy laminate. Tension tests in three directions provided six values of compliances, from which the method validates the in-plane isotropy assumption and gives the independent elastic constants. These examples prove that the method is effective, flexible and straightforward and should be of great interest in testing anisotropic composite materials.

INTRODUCTION

In the evaluation of mechanical properties of anisotropic composite materials a redundant set of tests is often required : (a) to improve the confidence and the accuracy of experimental data, (b) to assess the validity of a constitutive law, or (c) to determine all the independent material constants. The third point is clearly emphasized by the case of the anisotropic elastic constants, to which most of the attention will be given here ; generally, the engineering elastic constants (or the elastic stiffnesses, or the elastic compliances) cannot be separated in the usual tests, as for isotropic materials, and each test provides one or more quantities expressed in terms of the elastic coefficients ; further, the different tests generally give more quantities than coefficients to be measured, and these coefficients may be dependent due to some general constraint relations, such as symmetry conditions. At any rate, redundant quantities are obtained, which are not suited to conventional data processing.

So it should be useful to have a procedure which can obtain all the interrelated material constants for a prescribed material model from a set of dependent measured quantities. Such a procedure [1] (1980) is presented here and applied to a transversely isotropic material and an orthotropic material, which are the most currently used models for elastic composite materials. A comparison with the data averaging method of Wu et al. [2] (1973) for an orthotropic material is also given.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

The problem is to estimate p quantities $X_i (i = 1 - p)$ from their measurements, each quantity being associated with n_i experimental data $\bar{X}_{i,j} (j = 1 - n_i)$, to which different weights $W_{i,j}$ can be assigned to take into account their experimental confidence levels. The quantities X_i may be dependent variables constrained by q relations :

$$f_n(X_i) = 0 \quad (n = 1 - q) \quad (1)$$

and so must be the estimates X_i to be determined for the X_i :

$$f_n(X_i) = 0 \quad (n = 1 - q) \quad (2)$$

Obviously, there is no reason that the experimental data satisfy the constraints :

$$f_n(\bar{X}_{i,j}) \neq 0 \quad \text{for given } j \quad (3)$$

Let us introduce first a quantity E_m reckoning the deviation between the (unknown) estimates X_i and data $\bar{X}_{i,j}$, this quantity being always positive except when the data $\bar{X}_{i,j}$ have the same values and the estimates X_i are equal to these values, in which case $E_m = 0$. A wide variety of forms can be investigated for this deviation function E_m , however for reasons of convenience, we will consider only in the sequel square deviations, namely the weighted sums of the squares of absolute or relative deviations for the quantities X_i or their inverse Y_i :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2E_1 = \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} W_{i,j} (X_i - \bar{X}_{i,j})^2 \\ 2E_2 = \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} W_{i,j} \left(\frac{X_i - \bar{X}_{i,j}}{X_i} \right)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} W_{i,j} (1 - Y_i \bar{X}_{i,j})^2 \\ 2E_3 = \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} W_{i,j} (Y_i - \bar{Y}_{i,j})^2 \\ 2E_4 = \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} W_{i,j} \left(\frac{Y_i - \bar{Y}_{i,j}}{Y_i} \right)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} W_{i,j} (1 - X_i \bar{Y}_{i,j})^2 \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

where $Y_i = 1/X_i$ and $\bar{Y}_{ij} = 1/\bar{X}_{ij}$

The best estimating will be the one for which the deviation function E_m takes a minimum value. Of course, this "best" estimating can be expected to depend closely on the form of the deviation function. In fact, each deviation function provides its own best estimating. Further, from a mathematical point of view, these "best estimates" cannot be obtained by a direct minimization process, because the X_i are dependent variables constrained by the equations (2).

The algebra to obtain a set of independent variables extracted from the equations (2) may be terrible, even though the conditions (2) are generally rational. So we were quickly convinced of using the classical method of Lagrange multipliers. Introducing q Lagrange multipliers k_n (one for each condition (2)), a modified deviation function is constructed :

$$C_m = E_m + \sum_{n=1}^q k_n f_n \quad (5)$$

The Lagrange multipliers method consists then in a direct extremization of C_m with respect to the independent variables X_i and k_n . In the present case, it yields a system of $p + q$ equations :

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial}{\partial X_i} (E_m + \sum_{n=1}^q k_n f_n) = 0 & (i = 1 - p) \\ f_n = 0 & (n = 1 - q) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Generally, this system involves non-linear equations. It can be solved by an iterative numerical method. In the present study, we chose the Newton iterative method for the sake of simplicity.

APPLICATION TO A TRANSVERSALY

ISOTROPIC MATERIAL

Composite materials with unidirectional fibre reinforcement are usually taken as transversely isotropic materials in their macroscopic behaviour. Consequently, they have five independent elastic constants, which can be taken as (see Fig.1) :

E_{11} , the longitudinal Young's modulus (i.e. the modulus in the direction of the fibres),

$E_{22} = E_{33}$, the transverse Young's modulus (i.e., the modulus in any direction perpendicular to the fibres),

$G_{12} = G_{13}$, the in-plane shear modulus (i.e., the modulus in any plane parallel to the fibres),

$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$, the Poisson's ratio for longitudinal stress,

$\nu_{23} = \nu_{32}$, the transverse Poisson's ratio.

The other engineering constants can be expressed in terms of these constants. First, the other Poisson's ratios are given by the well-known reciprocal relations :

$$\frac{\nu_{ij}}{E_{ii}} = \frac{\nu_{ji}}{E_{jj}} \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3 \quad (7)$$

and the transverse shear modulus satisfies the transverse isotropy condition :

$$2G_{23} = \frac{E_{22}}{1 + \nu_{23}} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 1

We studied T 300/5208 graphite epoxy unidirectional laminates, made of 8 and 16 plies, with a percentage of fibres by volume from 62 % to 65 %. We made tests on plates and torsion tests of rods with rectangular cross section [3] (1977), [4] (1978). All the strain measurements were performed with electric strain gauges (Fig.2). The longitudinal tension test provided us with E_{11} and ν_{12} , while the transverse tension

Fig. 2

test gave E_{22} , ν_{21} and ν_{23} . The torsion around the fibres direction gave the in-plane shear modulus G_{12} and the torsion around the transverse direction gave the transverse shear modulus G_{23} , in addition to G_{12} , which was consequently measured by two ways: Table 1 gives the values for the 7 engineering constants E_{11} , E_{22} , ν_{12} , ν_{21} , ν_{23} , G_{23} and G_{12} obtained from these 8 measurements.

Quantity	E ₁₁ (MPa)	E ₂₂ (MPa)	v ₁₂	v ₂₁	v ₂₃	G ₂₃ (MPa)	G ₁₂ (MPa)
	\bar{X}_{1i}	\bar{X}_{2i}	\bar{X}_{3i}	\bar{X}_{4i}	\bar{X}_{5i}	\bar{X}_{6i}	
Measured values	142365	9084	0.36	0.024	0.44	3061	4336
	128358	8868	0.33	0.027	0.54	3659	4866
	150348	8888	0.37	0.027	0.46	3404	4532
	143984	9202	0.34	0.021	/	/	5111 [†]
	130320	10212	0.284	0.026	/	/	5268 [†]
	148608	8947	0.264	0.020	/	/	5013 [†]
Mean values	142161	/	/	/	/	/	/
Mean values	140878	9167	0.325	0.024	0.48	3375	4854

† : obtained from torsion around the fibres direction.

Table 1 - Measured and mean values of engineering elastic constants for graphite-epoxy unidirectional composite.

These measured values, as well as the mean values, do not satisfy the conditions (7) and (8), the deviation being respectively of about 12 % and 8 %, which is not too bad indeed. However, to enforce these conditions, we used the proposed method with the four deviation functions given in Eq.(4). Hereafter, the case of the relative square deviation for the quantities is developed. It may be noticed that the in-plane shear modulus G₁₂ is not involved in the conditions (7) and (8), so that it can be subjected to classical statistical methods. The other dependant quantities are written as follows :

$$\begin{cases} E_{11} = X_1 = 1/Y_1 & v_{21} = X_4 = 1/Y_4 \\ E_{22} = X_2 = 1/Y_2 & v_{23} = X_5 = 1/Y_5 \\ v_{12} = X_3 = 1/Y_3 & G_{23} = X_6 = 1/Y_6 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Then, the two conditions (7) and (8) can be put into the forms :

$$\begin{cases} f_1 = Y_1 Y_4 - Y_2 Y_3 = 0 \\ f_2 = 2Y_2(1 + Y_5) - Y_5 Y_6 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Further, we suppose that all the data have the same confidence level, i.e. all the weights W_{ij} are taken equal to 1. Then the modified deviation function is written:

$$C_2 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^6 \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (1 - Y_{ij} \bar{X}_{ij})^2 + X_7 f_1 + X_8 f_2 \quad (11)$$

where X₇ and X₈ are the Lagrange multipliers.

Performing the extremization of C₂ gives the following non linear system of 8 equations :

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial C_2}{\partial Y_i} = 0 & i = (1 - 6) \\ f_1 = 0 \\ f_2 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

This non-linear algebraic system was solved using the Newton iterative method implemented on a Tektronix 4051 microcomputer computing with 14 significant digits. The programme written in Basic, needs only a part of the microcomputer central memory, which is 16 K bytes large.

As the Newton method is an iterative process, it was necessary to study the convergence of the solution. The convergence tests showed (Table 2) that : (a) the precision requested (fixed by the maximum ϵ of the absolute value of the remainder) has little influence on the rate of convergence and the accuracy of the results X_i , (b) the initial values X_i^0 in the iterative process have on the contrary a pronounced influence. However, the choice of initial values X_i^0 ($i = 1 - 6$) approximately equal to their respective experimental means gives convergence within the minimum number of iterations. Therefore, this natural choice is also the best one, as it could be guessed. Finally, it can be noticed that the deviation function E_2 seems to give the best convergence.

Precision and initial values \ Deviation function	E_1	E_2	E_3	E_4
$\epsilon = 10^{-2}$; $X_i^0 = 1$ ($i = 1 - 8$)	†			
$\epsilon = 10^{-4}$; $X_i^0 = 1$ ($i = 1 - 8$)	†			
$\epsilon = 10^{-4}$; $X_i^0 = 160000$ ($i = 1 - 8$)	†			
$\epsilon = 10^{-4}$; $X_i^0 = \text{means}$ ($i = 1 - 6$); $X_7^0 = X_8^0 = 1$	5			
$\epsilon = 10^{-6}$; $X_i^0 = \text{means}$ ($i = 1 - 6$); $X_7^0 = X_8^0 = 1$				10
$\epsilon = 10^{-6}$; $Y_i^0 = \text{means}$ ($i = 1 - 6$); $Y_7^0 = Y_8^0 = 1$		5	4	
$\epsilon = 10^{-6}$; $X_i^0 = 160000$ ($i = 1 - 8$)				††
$\epsilon = 10^{-6}$; $Y_i^0 = 50$ ($i = 1 - 8$)		6	†	
$\epsilon = 10^{-4}$; $X_i^0 = Y_i^0 = 1$ ($i = 1 - 8$)		6	42	12
$\epsilon = 10^{-8}$; $X_i^0 = Y_i^0 = 1$ ($i = 1 - 8$)		7	43	12

† : non valid solution
 †† : solution not found after 50 iterations

Table 1 - Number of iterations for different precision, initial values and deviation functions.

The estimates X_i given by the analysis are slightly below the mean experimental values (Table 3), except for the transverse Young modulus. There is little difference between the results obtained for the various deviation functions. A choice between these deviation functions can be done with the two following criteria : (a) the evaluations X_i must lie within the data range, (b) the evaluation must be close to the mean experimental values. The deviation function E_2 which was just above referred to as the best for the convergence of the solution is also the best for these criteria. Of course all the deviation functions give evaluations satisfying exactly the conditions (7) and (8).

It should be emphasized that the values in Table 3 are given with many digits for numeric purposes only. Of course, experimental errors remove the significance of the last digits.

Evaluations (moduli in MPa)	E_{11} (X_1)	E_{22} (X_2)	ν_{12} (X_3)	ν_{21} (X_4)	ν_{23} (X_5)	G_{23} (X_6)	G_{12}
Mean experi- mental values	140878	9167	0.325	0.024	0.480	3375	4854
Data range	$\begin{cases} 128358 \\ 150348 \end{cases}$	$\begin{cases} 8868 \\ 10212 \end{cases}$	$\begin{cases} 0.264 \\ 0.37 \end{cases}$	$\begin{cases} 0.02 \\ 0.027 \end{cases}$	$\begin{cases} 0.44 \\ 0.54 \end{cases}$	$\begin{cases} 3061 \\ 3659 \end{cases}$	$\begin{cases} 4336 \\ 5268 \end{cases}$
Deviation function E_1	140877.71	9200.17	0.325	0.0212	0.363 [†]	3374.67	/
Deviation function E_2	138039.62	9694.70	0.339	0.0238	0.478	3278.81	/
Deviation function E_3	131086.26	9766.07	0.320	0.0238	0.476	3307.61	/
Deviation function E_4	136177.27	9542.42	0.324	0.0227	0.469	3248.29	/
Comparison to data averages	lower	higher	—	lower	lower	lower	/

† : out of data range

Table 3 - Evaluations of elastic constants for a transversely isotropic material for various deviation functions. Rounding required by experimental errors not performed.

APPLICATION TO
AN ORTHOTROPIC MATERIAL

Measurement of the compliance tensor $S_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ for an orthotropic composite material under plane stress can be made by a series of tests performed for different directions. Each test gives one or several components of the compliance tensor relative to the coordinates defined by the direction of the off-axis test (Fig.3).

Fig. 3

In these coordinates, the generalized Hooke's law expresses the strains $\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}$ in function of the stresses $\sigma_{\alpha\beta}$ in the tensorial form (with the usual summation convention) :

$$\epsilon_{\alpha\beta} = S_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \sigma_{\gamma\delta} \quad (13)$$

or in the matrix form :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \epsilon_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{xxxx} & S_{xxxy} & S_{xxxxy} \\ S_{yyxx} & S_{yyxy} & S_{yyxxy} \\ S_{xyxx} & S_{xyxy} & S_{xyxxy} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ 2\sigma_{xy} \end{pmatrix} \quad (14)$$

The components appearing in these formulas are functions of the angle θ and of the components in the material symmetry coordinates, which are the quantities sought for.

Wu et al. [2] (1973) studied this problem and described in their paper a procedure based on the use of four of the five invariants of two dimensionnal 4th rank tensor [5] (1974), [6] (1979). This method has a serious disadvantage, namely it needs the values of all the components of the tensor for each direction. The measurements of all these quantities are generally not possible, and, at any rate, expensive. For instance, Wu et al. performed tension and torsion tests of tubular cylinders with fibres oriented in various directions θ_m . Even with these special specimens, which are very expensive and may present some difference with the real structure due to difference in the manufacturing process, Wu et al. obtained only five of the six components, the sixth (transverse Young modulus) being deduced from symmetry considerations.

The application of the present method do not require all the components in the considered directions to determine averaged consistent values of the anisotropic constants. It can be described as follows. Let X be the tensor associated with some physical anisotropic property. Whatever the rank of the tensor may be, it is possible, and convenient, to represent its components by vectors (of appropriate dimension q_0). So the tensorial transformation relations connecting the components in two different systems of coordinates can be written in the following matrix form :

$$\{x(\theta)\} = [t(\theta)] \{x^0\} \quad (15)$$

where x_k^0 ($k = 1 - q_0$) are the components in the material reference system of coordinates, x_h ($h = 1 - q_0$) are the components in the system of coordinates obtained from the reference system by a rotation θ , and $t_{hk}(\theta)$ ($h, k = 1 - q_0$) are the elements of the square matrix of transformation, depending on the angle of rotation and the rank of the tensor.

Suppose now that an experimental procedure provides measurements of a part q of the q_0 components in some directions θ_m ($m = 1 - p$). Let $X_{i'}(\theta_m)$ ($i' = 1 - q < q_0$) be these components, N_{im} the number of measurements for each i' and m , and $\bar{X}_{i'jm}$ ($j = 1 - N_{im}$) the measured values of $X_{i'}(\theta_m)$. These components must satisfy the tensorial transformation relations obtained from Eq. (15) by restricting to the appropriate components :

$$\{X(\theta_m)\} = [T(\theta_m)] \{x^0\} \quad (m = 1 - p) \quad (16)$$

where $T_{i'k}(\theta)$ ($i' = 1 - q$, $k = 1 - q_0$) are the elements of the lines of the matrix $[t(\theta)]$ corresponding to the measured components, and so must do the evaluations $X_{i'}(\theta_m)$ ($i' = 1 - q$) for the $X_{i'}(\theta_m)$ and the evaluations x_k^0 ($k = 1 - q_0$) for the x^0 :

$$\{X(\theta_m)\} = [T(\theta_m)] \{x^0\} \quad (m = 1 - p) \quad (17)$$

Of course, the measured values $\bar{X}_{i'jm}$ do not satisfy such relations.

Any deviation function can be used. Taking hereafter the absolute square deviation function E_1 gives :

$$E_1 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{i=1}^q \sum_{j=1}^{N_{im}} W_{ijm} [X_{i,jm}(\theta_m) - \bar{X}_{i,jm}]^2 \quad (18)$$

where the W_{ijm} are the weights assigned to the experimental values $\bar{X}_{i,jm}$.

In this case, the constraints (17) can be eliminated easily, and the use of Lagrange multipliers is unnecessary. The following expression for E_1 in terms of x_k^o is then found :

$$E_1 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{i=1}^q \sum_{j=1}^{N_{im}} W_{ijm} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{q_0} T_{ik}(\theta_m) x_k^o - \bar{X}_{i,jm} \right]^2 \quad (19)$$

which can be minimized directly with respect to the variables x_k^o .

This minimization gives a system of q_0 linear equations in the q_0 variables x_k^o :

$$[\alpha] \{x^o\} = \{\beta\} \quad (20)$$

where the coefficients have the following values :

$$\alpha_{hk} = \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{i=1}^q \left[T_{ih}(\theta_m) T_{ik}(\theta_m) \sum_{j=1}^{N_{im}} W_{ijm} \right] \quad (21)$$

$$\beta_k = \sum_{m=1}^p \sum_{i=1}^q \left[T_{ik}(\theta_m) \sum_{j=1}^{N_{im}} W_{ijm} \bar{X}_{i,jm} \right] \quad (22)$$

$$(h, k = 1 - q_0)$$

It can be noticed that the matrix $[\alpha]$ is symmetrical. It is regular, provided that the total number pxq of measured quantities is sufficient ($pxq > q_0$ is necessary and may be sufficient).

Obviously, once the estimations x_k^o for *all* the components of the tensor in the material reference coordinates are obtained from Eq.(20), it is easy to compute the components in any other system of coordinates, and so particularly the estimates $X_{i,jm}$.

It can be pointed out from the procedure outlined that it is *not necessary* to have at disposal measured values for all the components in the various coordinate systems.

In order to assess the value of the method, it was applied to the case and the data published by Wu et al.. They determined experimentally five components (excepting S_{yyyy}) of the compliance tensor $S_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ for seven directions θ_m ($0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ, 90^\circ$) and the mean values are listed in Table 4 (for obvious numerical reasons, the original units of Wu et al., i.e. British units, are used throughout this comparison study, and no SI equivalent is given). By combining these data by symmetrization, Wu et al. constructed values of all the six components of the compliance tensor, listed in Table 5. Further, the material is supposed to be orthotropic in the $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ directions.

Direction	S_{xxxx}	S_{xyxy}	$2S_{xxyy}$	S_{yyyy}	$2S_{xyyy}$	$4S_{xyxy}$
0°	0.059	-0.023	0.000	†	0.000	1.402
15°	0.115	-0.053	0.300	†	0.020	1.265
30°	0.309	-0.090	0.418	†	0.195	1.017
45°	0.496	-0.126	0.390	†	0.338	0.896
60°	0.661	-0.080	0.211	†	0.309	1.094
75°	0.864	-0.067	0.137	†	0.389	1.345
90°	0.892	-0.036	0.000	†	0.000	1.359

† : not measured

Table 4 - Measured compliance coefficients (in 10^{-6}psi^{-1}), from Wu et al.[2].

Directions	S_{xxxx} (S_{yyyy})	S_{xxyy} (S_{xyxy})	$2S_{xxyy}$ ($2S_{xyxy}$)	S_{yyyy} (S_{xxxx})	$2S_{xyyy}$ ($2S_{xxyy}$)	$4S_{xyxy}$ ($4S_{xyxy}$)
0° (90°)	0.059	-0.028	0.000	0.892	0.000	1.380
15° (75°)	0.115	-0.057	0.318	0.864	0.078	1.292
30° (60°)	0.308	-0.085	0.381	0.661	0.206	1.055
45° (45°)	0.496	-0.126	0.390	0.496	0.338	0.896

Table 5 - Symmetrized compliance coefficients (in 10^{-6} psi $^{-1}$) used by Wu et al.

At this point, it may be useful to recall the tensorial transformation formulas for such an orthotropic material :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 S_{xxxx} = S_{1111} c^4 + 2(S_{1122} + 2S_{1212})c^2\delta^2 + S_{2222} \delta^4 \\
 S_{yyyy} = S_{1111} \delta^4 + 2(S_{1122} + 2S_{1212})c^2\delta^2 + S_{2222} c^4 \\
 S_{xxyy} = (S_{1111} + S_{2222} - 4S_{1212})c^2\delta^2 + S_{1122}(c^4 + \delta^4) \\
 S_{xyxy} = (S_{1111} + S_{2222} - 2S_{1122})c^2\delta^2 + S_{1212}(c^2 - \delta^2)^2 \\
 S_{xxyy} = c\delta\{-S_{1111}c^2 + (S_{1122} + 2S_{1212})(c^2 - \delta^2) + S_{2222}\delta^2\} \\
 S_{yyxy} = -c\delta\{-S_{1111}\delta^2 + (S_{1122} + 2S_{1212})(\delta^2 - c^2) + S_{2222}c^2\}
 \end{array} \right. \quad (23)$$

where $c = \cos \theta_m$ and $\delta = -\sin \theta_m$

By rotating the off-angle values of Table 5 to 0°, it can be noted (in Table 6) that these values do not at all agree with one another, nor even with an orthotropic behaviour (non zero values for S_{1112} and S_{1222}).

Direction and rotation angle	S_{1111}	S_{1122}	$2S_{1112}$	S_{2222}	$2S_{1222}$	$4S_{1212}$
0°	0.059	-0.028	0	0.892	0	1.380
15°	0.0266	-0.0175	0.0011	0.8733	-0.0327	1.4501
30°	0.0884	-0.0314	-0.0317	0.7733	0.0195	1.2696
45°	0.0450	-0.0390	-0.0260	0.7730	0.0260	1.2440

Table 6 - Values obtained from Table 5 by rotation to 0°.

A first estimate via the present method was obtained using the values of Table 5, with the deviation function E_1 . It is shown in Table 7. The same deviation function was also used to construct an estimate directly from the measured incomplete values of Table 4. The precision of the method can be assessed from the values (Table 7) reached by the following deviation e , used by Wu et al. :

$$e = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^4}{m \sum_{j=1}^6} [X_j(\theta_m) - \bar{X}_{mj}]^2 \quad (24)$$

	S_{1111}	S_{1122}	$2S_{1112}$	S_{2222}	$2S_{2212}$	$4S_{1212}$	e
Symmetrized values at 0°	0.059	-0.028	0	0.892	0	1.380	0.0545
Wu et al.	0.0536	-0.0280	0	0.8266	0	1.3403	0.0298
First estimate	0.0497	-0.0289	0	0.8229	0	1.3710	0.0278
Second estimate	0.0627	-0.0244	0	0.8206	0	1.3906	0.0295

Table 7 - Estimated values (in 10^{-6} psi $^{-1}$) and deviations.

It can be seen that our method is more accurate than that of Wu et al. with their own criterion, even with the second estimate for which this criterion, based on the values of Table 5, is not at all suitable. The advantage of our method is even greater than shown by this accuracy improvement, and lies mainly in the fact that the process can be developed from the very measured values without questionable transformations.

APPLICATION TO
A QUASI - ISOTROPIC LAMINATE

We studied also a symmetric laminate with eight layers of the same unidirectional graphite epoxy material as studied in the previous application. The stacking sequence was :

$$[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_{\text{symmetric}} \quad (25)$$

so that, according to the classical lamination theory, the laminate should be isotropic with regard to the in-plane behaviour. Tension tests in three directions (0° , 45° and 90°) were performed and provided experimental values for the components S_{xxxx}^θ and S_{xyyy}^θ (x being the direction of tension and θ the angle with respect to the first material axis, as shown in Fig.4).

Fig. 4

These experimental values are given in Table 8 (four values for each quantity), together with their arithmetic average. As in the other applications the numerous digits of the values are retained only for numerical process.

	Experimental values				Average
S_{xxxx}°	19.59178172	18.57306141	20.27744821	19.33866784	19.44523979
S_{yyxx}°	-5.05990267	-6.091597896	-6.18135948	-6.140771035	-5.86840777
$S_{xxxx}^{-45^{\circ}}$	18.89810802	18.90480674	19.57145941	19.10352871	19.11947572
$S_{yyxx}^{-45^{\circ}}$	-5.84936014	-5.652792058	-5.542754564	-5.387495332	-5.608100523
$S_{xxxx}^{90^{\circ}}$	18.91179633	19.78624524	19.56887805	19.62594519	19.4732162
$S_{yyxx}^{90^{\circ}}$	-5.137623368	-5.206967318	-5.506525453	-5.584965986	-5.359020531

Table 8 - Measured compliances and mean values in 3 directions for T300/5208 quasi-isotropic laminate.

The method was applied assuming that the laminate was orthotropic, and consequently used the same analysis as the previous application. The compliance tensor components were obtained in the laminate material coordinates (Table 9), and the engineering constants E_{xx} , E_{yy} , ν_{xy} and G_{xy} shown in Table 10 were afterwards deduced from these components.

	Orthotropic assumption	
	Deviation E_1	Deviation E_4
S_{xxxx}	19.39059169	19.29214722
S_{xxyy}	-5.67461226	-5.564144777
S_{yyyy}	19.41856809	19.34624043
S_{xyxy}	12.36378812	12.45652372

Table 9 - Compliance tensor components (in 10^{-12} Pa^{-1}) estimated in the material coordinates ($S_{xxxy} = S_{xyyy} = 0$)

The obtained estimates are orthotropic and not exactly isotropic. However, the isotropy relations are approximately satisfied by the estimates, the condition $E_{xx} = E_{yy}$ being satisfied with an error less than 0,3 % and the conditions $2G_{xy}(1 + \nu_{xy}) = E_{xx}$ with an error less than 1,4 %. These very small errors validate a further assumption of quasi-isotropy, and Table 10 shows isotropic values (obtained by averaging) and also values obtained from the classical lamination theory applied to the values obtained for the unidirectional material.

	Deviation E (orthotropic)	Deviation E (orthotropic)	Isotropic values	Classical lamination theory
E_{xxx} (MPa)	51571.40	51834.56	51690.33	53888.49
E_{yyy} (MPa)	51497.10	51689.63	51690.33	53888.49
ν_{xy}	0.293	0.288	0.290	0.318
G_{xy} (MPa)	20220.34	20069.80	20033.80	20449.93

Table 10 - Engineering constants evaluated by various processes.

CONCLUSION

We presented in this paper a new process for determining interrelated material constants from dependent measured quantities obtained with a redundant set of tests. It consists in minimizing some deviation function, modified in case of need using Lagrange multipliers to take into account the constraint relations. The method was applied to three different cases of determination of elastic constants, a unidirectional composite and a quasi-isotropic laminate, which we tested by ourselves, and an orthotropic laminate for which testing results were found in the literature. The method proved to be effective, with two main advantages : (a) all the experimental data can be used, possibly with weights representative of their confidence levels, (b) no transformation is required for the data, which can be used with their original experimental values. It can be concluded that this study provides a general process for systematic determination of material constants from redundant experimental data. This process can be very useful for testing anisotropic composite material, as it was demonstrated. Moreover, its application can be obviously extended to other fields of experimental mechanics.

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